

α -Oximino- β -substituted Hydrazones of Acetoacetarylamides

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Forty three new compounds have been prepared by condensing different hydrazides and α -oximino-acetoacetarylamides with a view to studying them from different aspects.

Several investigators¹⁻³ have found that hydrazones with an oximino group are of some biological interest by virtue of the presence of the $-\text{CONH}-\text{N}=\text{C}-$ group and the $=\text{NOH}$ group, which impart antiparasitic, fungicidal, and bactericidal properties to such compounds.

Dave and Talati^{3,4} have shown that $\alpha\beta$ -dioximes of acetoacetarylamides can be utilised as chelating agents for the quantitative estimation of transitional metals, such as Ni, Co, Cu, and Pd, either alone or in presence of one another.

Taylor *et al.*⁵ have reported an obvious analogy between the oxime-hydrazones and the vic-dioximes of benzil by studying the chelation properties of their stereoisomers with the transitional metals, such as Fe (II), Ni, Pd, and Co.

In view of the above, it was considered worthwhile to undertake a systematic study of α -oximino-hydrazones of acetoacetarylamides and to obtain some information regarding their stereochemistry, chelating ability with transitional metals, an analogy with the corresponding dioximes, and their biological activity. The present communication deals with the preparation of β -substituted hydrazones of α -oximinoacetoacetarylamides.

EXPERIMENTAL

α -Oximino-acetoacetarylamides (13) were prepared by the method of Knorr⁶ and except α -oximino-acetoacet-*m*- and -*p*-chloro and -*p*-bromo anilides, all were crystallised from chloroform and petroleum (40:60) mixture. The above mentioned three compounds were crystallised from aqueous ethanol. Out of these, five compounds have been prepared for the first time. Their m.p. and analysis (micro) are recorded in Table I.

1. Giammanco, *Ann. chim.*, 1901, 51, 175.
2. Misra and Varma, *this Journal*, 1962, 39, 763.
3. *Ibid.*, 1959, 36, 179, 302, 735, 839.
4. *Idem, ibid.*, 1960, 37, 40.
5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 257.
6. *Annalen*, 1887, 236, 80.

TABLE I

α-Oximino-acetoacetarylamides.
[A denotes α-oximino-acetoacet]

Amides.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.
†A- <i>m</i> -chloroanilide	152°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	11.82	11.64
*A- <i>p</i> -anisidide	133°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	12.05	11.96
‡A-2,4-dimethoxyanilide	159°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₂	10.45	10.53
*A-2,5-dichloroanilide	135°	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	10.29	10.18
†A- <i>p</i> -bromoanilide	180°	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂ Br	10.01	9.83

†White in colour.
*Yellow ,,
‡Orange ,,

Preparation of α-Oximino-β-substituted Hydrazones.— Condensation of the α-oximino-acetoacetarylamides with the hydrazides, viz., semicarbazide, thiosemicarbazide, benzoylhydrazide, and salicylhydrazide, was carried out by taking α-oximino-acetoacetarylamides in ethanol and aqueous solutions of hydrazides in equimolecular proportions and a few drops of HCl (conc.). On keeping for 2-3 hr., the product separating was filtered and crystallised from aqueous ethanol. In all the cases the yield obtained was within the range of 75% to 90%. The characteristics and analysis (micro) are shown in Tables II and III.

TABLE II**

Semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones.

[A denotes α-oximino-acetoacet]

No.	Amides.	M.P.	Semicarbazones.		Thiosemicarbazones.		
			Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.
1	A-anilide	147-48°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ †	26.50 26.61	176-77°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S ⁺	25.15 25.10
2	A- <i>o</i> -toluidide	174°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ †	25.10 25.27	152°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ S ⁺	23.84 23.88
3	A- <i>p</i> -toluidide	162°	,, *	25.00 ,,	175°	,, †	23.95 ,,
4	A- <i>o</i> -chloroanilide	172°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl†	23.45 23.53	160-62°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ ClS*	22.10 22.33
5	A- <i>m</i> -chloroanilide	154°	,, *	23.30 ,,	180°	,, †	22.20 ,,
6	A- <i>p</i> -chloroanilide	158°	,, *	23.58 ,,	170°	,, †	22.46 ,,
7	A- <i>o</i> -anisidide	168-70°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃ ‡	24.00 23.90	159°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃ S ⁺	22.60 22.65
8	A- <i>p</i> -anisidide	170-72°	,, †	24.05 ,,	171°	,, ‡	22.75 ,,
9	A- <i>m</i> -xylidide(2,4)	195°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ †	23.90 24.06	187.89°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S†	22.90 22.81
10	A-2,4-dimethoxy-anilide	158-60°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₃ ‡	21.75 21.67	178°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S*	20.45 20.65
11	A- <i>p</i> -phenetidide	161°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ †	22.60 22.81	170°	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ S*	21.50 21.67

**Melts with decomposition.

†White in colour.

* Light yellow ,,

‡Yellow ,,

TABLE III

[A denotes α -oximino-acetoacet]

No.	Amides.	‡M.P.	Benzoyl hydrazones.			Salicyl hydrazones.		
			Formula.	%Nitrogen.		Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.
1	A-nilide	120°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ *	17.05	17.20	180-82°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ *	16.60 16.50
2	A-o-toluidide	154°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄ *	16.35	16.57	111°	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₄ N ₄ *	15.70 15.82
3	A-p-toluidide	168°	" *	16.40	"	186°	" **	15.62 "
4	A-o-chloroanilide	155°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₄ Cl*	15.40	15.63	185°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₄ Cl*	15.14 14.95
5	A-m-chloroanilide	162°	" *	15.37	"	183°	" *	15.20 "
6	A-p-chloroanilide	183°	" *	15.45	"	198°	" **	15.22 "
7	A-o-anisidide	130°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ *	15.65	15.82	190-92°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₄ *	15.00 15.14
8	A-p-anisidide	166°	" *	15.70	"	178-81°	" **	15.25 "
9	A-m-xylidide (2,4)	158°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₄ †	16.05	15.92	146°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ **	14.95 15.22
10	A-2,4-dimethoxy-anilide	..	..	..	..	173°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₄ *	13.90 14.00
11	A-p-phenetidide	160°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄ **	15.11	15.22	175-78°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄ **	14.92 14.59

‡Melts with decomposition.

*White in colour.

†Light yellow.

**Yellow.

DISCUSSION

α -Oximino- β -substituted hydrazones have been assigned *anti*-configuration as shown below:

[where R=aryl group and R'=-CONH₂,-CSNH₂, COC₆H₅, COO₆H₄(OH) *ortho*..]

This configuration has been confirmed by preparing forty three palladium and five nickel chelates. On the basis of analysis, magnetic properties, and UV spectra of the parent compounds, the following structure with square-planar configuration has been assigned to the chelates.

The representative members, viz., semicarbazone, benzoylhydrazone, and, salicylhydrazone of α -oximino-acetoacetanilide and *o*-toluidide, used for the quantitative estimation of palladium from its salt solution in presence and absence of other cations at different pH, have been found to be suitable analytical agents. The characteristics and analyses (micro) of the palladium chelates are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Palladium chelates of α -oximino- β -substituted hydrazones.[A denotes α -oximino-acetoacet]

No.	Amides.	M.P. (decomp.).	Composition of chelates.	Colour.	Found.	Reqd.
Semicarbazones.						
1	A-anilide	268°	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₁₀ Pd	Bright yellow	Pd : 17.12 N : 22.30	16.92 22.20
2	A-o-toluidide	265°	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₁₀ Pd	Golden "	Pd : 16.10 N : 21.24	16.20 21.25
Thiosemicarbazones.						
3	A-anilide	178°	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Pd	Red	Pd : 16.16 N : 21.05	16.10 21.12
4	A-o-toluidide	208°	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₄ N ₁₀ S ₂ Pd	Orange-red	Pd : 15.32 N : 20.18	15.45 20.27
Benzoylhydrazones.						
5	A-anilide	315°	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ O ₆ N ₈ Pd	Bright yellow	Pd : 14.28 N : 14.97	14.18 14.88
6	A-o-toluidide	318°	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ O ₆ N ₈ Pd	"	Pd : 13.58 N : 14.27	13.67 14.35
Salicylhydrazones.						
7	A-anilide.	307°	C ₃₄ H ₃₀ O ₈ N ₈ Pd	"	Pd : 13.45 N : 14.16	13.60 14.27
8	A-o-toluidide	303°	C ₃₆ H ₃₄ O ₈ N ₈ Pd	"	Pd : 13.13 N : 13.92	13.12 13.78

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